

Knowledge Regulation Skills and English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City

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Abstract. The current study evaluated the domains of knowledge regulation skills that significantly influence the English literature insights of students. In this study, the researcher selected 155 junior high school students in District 1, Davao City, as the respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Linear Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that students' knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights in District 1, Davao City, were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. Linear regression analysis found that knowledge regulation skills in terms of information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, and debugging strategies are significant predictors of English literature insights. In other words, knowledge regulation skills significantly influence the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City.

KEY WORDS 1. Teaching English 2. Knowledge Regulation Skills 3. English Literature Insights Of Students

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1. Introduction

Several researches indicated that lack of interest in English literature among students remains a perennial concern. Students' positive perception of the study of literature helps develop an understanding of the teaching and learning process in the literature context. Students with positive perceptions towards the study of literature will be more willing to learn the literature. They will develop strategies to accomplish tasks such as asking questions, volunteering information, and answering questions. Moreover, teaching through literature has been an integral part of developing students' capacity to become literate citizens since it polishes the skills of our students in reading, writing, listening, and speaking. In the Philippines, with different approaches and designs for classes, whether by literary competence, reading competence, or language arts competence focused curriculum, the teaching of literature helps students to practice these macro skills and to refine their critical thinking and creativity. Several authors

reported that poor English literature insights among students can have several consequences and implications that impact their educational experiences and personal development. For instance, Naser and Aziz (2017) found that students with poor insights into English literature may struggle to appreciate and enjoy the richness of literary works. This can lead to missed opportunities for personal enrichment through reading. Also, Al-Saggaf, et al. (2021) reported that poor literature insights may lead to difficulties in expressing ideas, articulating thoughts, and engaging in effective written and oral communication. Adding more, Wasti (2016) found that a lack of literary insights leads to a narrowed worldview. Exposure to diverse characters and perspectives in literature broadens one's horizons and empathy, fostering a more inclusive and open-minded perspective. In the Philippines, Sarce (2021) reported that poor insights limit students' ability to participate actively in discussions and debates. In addition, Deyto (2020) asserted that poor literary insights result in a deprivation of these cultural and aesthetic experiences. As Batteson et al. (2014) pointed out, knowledge regulation skills enable students to become more self-directed learners. They learn to set goals, plan their study routines, and evaluate their progress independently. This self-directedness is crucial for lifelong learning and academic success. These skills equip students to identify learning difficulties or gaps in their understanding. They can employ strategies to address these challenges, leading to more effective problem-solving and critical-thinking abilities. In addition, Poth (2019) asserted that students who regulate their knowledge effectively tend to manage their time more efficiently. They can prioritize tasks, allocate their study time wisely, and avoid procrastination, resulting in increased productivity. Likewise, Owen and Vista (2017) affirmed that the ability to regulate one's knowledge contributes to motivation and engagement in learning. Meanwhile, researchers have found a significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and students' English literature insights. However, those studies were conducted in a foreign setting and utilized qualitative approaches. As an example, the study of Akin (2016) showed that students with knowledge regulation skills are more likely to employ effective study strategies when approaching English literature. They may use summarization, annotation, and note-taking techniques to extract key themes, character development, and plot details from texts. Also, Zhang and Seepho (2013) concluded that students who regulate their knowledge are more likely to reflect on their understanding of literature, identify areas of confusion, and seek clarification. This metacognitive awareness helps them bridge gaps in comprehension. Likewise, the qualitative study by Memiş and Kandemir (2019) indicated that students with knowledge regulation skills frequently self-assess their progress and understanding. They can evaluate their insights into the literature, recognizing areas they may need to revisit or explore further. This self-assessment leads to an improved understanding of the material. While a substantial body of research examines factors that influence English literature insights among students, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the specific role of knowledge regulation skills in enhancing these insights. While existing studies suggest the importance of knowledge regulation skills in academic achievement, limited empirical evidence explores how these skills positively affect students' ability to comprehend, analyze, and interpret English literature. Regression analysis can help quantify the relationship between knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights, shedding light on the magnitude and significance of this influence, which is crucial for educators and students seeking to enhance the depth of understanding and engagement with literary texts. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research

gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive-correlational design to understand better the relationship between metacognitive awareness and perception of the study of literature among the students, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding students' insights in the literature. Thus, it is hoped that the methods of analysis and evaluation employed in this study, as well as the findings and recommendations that were made, would be helpful to teachers and school administration so that they could develop students' positive perceptions towards the study of literature.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section discusses knowledge regulation skills and literature insights, drawn from various studies and perspectives.

1.1.1. Knowledge Regulation Skills—Metacognition, defined as the ability to manage one's thinking processes, is crucial for effective learning (Jaleel Premachandran, 2016). It involves planning, monitoring, and evaluating cognitive performance. Students with metacognitive skills can think critically, solve problems, and make better decisions (Owen Vista, 2017; Naimnule Corebima, 2018). Research shows that metacognitive awareness enhances student learning, enabling them to recognize strengths and weaknesses (Bryce, Whitebread, Szűcs, 2015; Puspita, 2020). Learners who apply metacognitive strategies are more autonomous, self-motivated, and successful (Bereiter Scardamalia, 2014; Medina et al., 2017).

Metacognition involves key components: planning (Schraw Dennison, 1994), which enhances goal setting and resource allocation (Vallin, 2019); information management (Al'Omairi Al Balushi, 2015), which improves focus and comprehension; comprehension monitoring (Hidayat, 2014), essential for assessing understanding; and debugging strategies

(Schraw Dennison, 1994), which help correct errors (Sil, 2017). Finally, evaluation helps students improve by analyzing performance and refining learning strategies (Dotson, 2016; Adnan Bahri, 2018).

1.1.2. Literature Insights—Studying literature enhances language proficiency and critical thinking (Paran Robinson, 2016; Othman et al., 2015). It offers a broader understanding of human nature, culture, and values, fostering empathy and social awareness (Alfauzan Hussain, 2017; Tevdovska, 2016). Literature also provides insight into social justice, reflecting societal norms and evolving cultural practices (Coles, 2019; Irene, 2015). Additionally, it highlights the impact of the environment on human life, showcasing the deep connection between nature and literature (Teranish et al., 2015; Sharma, 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher with the result of other research to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. Literature underscores the crucial role of knowledge regulation skills in shaping students' English literature insights. These metacognitive skills facilitate deeper comprehension, critical analysis, personal connection, and academic success in literary studies. Studies consistently demonstrate a positive relationship between knowledge regulation skills and improved reading comprehension in English literature. Students who effectively monitor their understanding, set goals for their reading, and self-assess their comprehension tend to achieve a deeper and more nuanced understanding of literary texts. As such, educators and students alike can benefit from a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—The current study was anchored on Zimmerman and Schunk's (2001) Self-Regulated Learning Theory (SRL). It contends that language

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

learning evolves from learning how to carry on conversations. Self-Regulated Learning Theory is particularly relevant to this study, emphasizing metacognitive processes and self-regulation skills. Students' knowledge regulation skills can be framed within metacognition, where they set goals, monitor their understanding of literary texts, and evaluate their comprehension. The study can explore how students use these skills to adapt their strategies for reading, interpreting, and engaging with English literature, ultimately impacting their insights. In support, Zhang and Seepho (2013) proposed that using metacognitive, planning, monitoring, and evaluating strategies correlated with their perception of the literature, respectively. Knowledge regulation skills are closely tied to metacognition, which involves thinking about one's thinking. Students who regulate their knowledge are more likely to reflect on their understanding of literature,

identify areas of confusion, and seek clarification. This metacognitive awareness helps them bridge gaps in comprehension. Moreover, Akin (2016) showed that students with knowledge regulation skills are likelier to employ effective study strategies when approaching English literature. They may use summarization, annotation, and note-taking techniques to extract key themes, character development, and plot details from texts. Students with knowledge regulation skills frequently self-assess their progress and understanding. They can evaluate their insights into the literature, recognizing areas they may need to revisit or explore further. This self-assessment leads to an improved understanding of the material. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable was knowledge regulation skills or the ability to manage one's thinking processes.

The measure of knowledge regulation skills, according to Schraw and Dennison (1994), are planning or the extent of goal setting and allocating resources prior to learning, information management strategy or the skills and strategy sequences used to process information more efficiently such as organizing, elaborating, summarizing and selective focusing, comprehension monitoring or the assessment of one's learning,

comprehension and strategy used, debugging strategies or the strategies used to correct comprehension and performance errors, and evaluation or the performance and strategy effectiveness after a learning episode. The dependent variable is English literature insight or the understanding of individuals concerning literature. According to Alfauzan and Hussain (2017), the measures of English literature insights are the

reaction of social justice or the fact that reflects the social justice prevailing in the society, understanding of human nature and values or the belief that literature expresses universal human nature, cultural clashes or the human clashes with cultural and religious identities, and impact of environment or the belief of the human that literature has an impact the environment

that surrounds them.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine the significant influence of knowledge regulation skills on the literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of knowledge regulation skills of the students in District 1, Davao City, in terms of:
 - (1) planning;
 - (2) Information Management Strategy;
 - (3) comprehension monitoring;
 - (4) debugging strategies; and
 - (5) evaluation?
- (2) What is the extent of the literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, in terms of:
 - (1) reaction to social justice;
 - (2) understanding of human nature and values;
 - (3) cultural clashes; and
 - (4) impact of environment?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City?
- (4) Which domains of knowledge regulation skills significantly influence the literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. H02: None of the domains of knowledge regulation skills significantly influence the literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. For a more comprehensive understanding,

the following terms were defined operationally: Knowledge Regulation Skills. This study describes the independent variable in planning, information management strategy, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation. English Literature Insights. This study describes the dependent variable as the following indicators: reaction to social justice, understanding of human nature and values, cultural clashes, and environmental impact.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence,

and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher investigated the relationship between variables, such as knowledge regulation skills and literature insights. In this connection, the study focused on the relationships among variables to determine the significance of the relationship between these variables. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were junior high school students in District 1, Davao City. The 155 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random

sampling was described as a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those enrolled junior high school students in District 1 Davao City who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the students' socio-economic status.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study used adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The scaling was done by using one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Also, the survey questionnaires underwent validation by an external and internal panel of experts. The first part is about the knowledge regulation skills of junior high school students adapted from the study of Schraw and Dennison (1994), which is composed of statements that were indicated with planning, information management strategy, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation. The new scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.934, which was described as excellent and interpreted as highly reliable and an item with internal consistency. As a guide in determining the extent of knowledge regulation skills of students, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The knowledge regulation skills of students are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The knowledge regulation skills of students are oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The knowledge regulation skills of students are sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The knowledge regulation skills of students are rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The knowledge regulation skills of students are never observed.

The second part of the instrument concerns the English literature insights adapted from the study of Alfauzan and Hussain (2017), which consists of statements divided into the reactions to social justice, understanding of human nature and values, cultural clashes, and the impact of the environment. The new scale obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.944, which was described as excellent and interpreted as highly reliable and an item with internal consistency. As a guide in determining the extent of English literature insights of students, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The English literature insights of students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The English literature insights of students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The English literature insights of students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The English literature insights of students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The English literature insights of students is never manifested.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher underwent the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. **Permission to Conduct the Study.** The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed by the principals of the selected public schools in District 1, Davao City. The researchers personally brought the letters to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher first appeared in the principal’s office in the second week of January 2023. However, due to the principals’ busy schedules, the researcher could not receive approval from the respective office. So, the researcher came back in the second week of February 2023. The approval from the respective offices was then granted. After that, the

researcher proceeded to distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the study was approved, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher conducted the survey simultaneously to administer the questionnaire. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study and given ample explanations so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote the

literature insights concerning knowledge regulation skills of the junior high school students in District 1 in Davao City and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents are junior high school students, so they are considered vulnerable since all of them are under legal age. They were also considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, which was the real source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the participants' privacy, it was assured that the researcher could only access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the online survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect aca-

demic information related to the study, and the participants were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the study's respondents—anybody who fits the qualifications of being a bona fide student in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication related to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher properly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that other factors like conflict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available if they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the study's success. The Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so they

could be accessed by the respondents and used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials, which were ample and available during the study and were done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by properly encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing junior high school student's knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights in District 1, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (knowledge regulation skills) and dependent (English literature insights) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the significant influence of knowledge regulation skills on the English literature insights of junior high school students in District 1, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights of the students in District 1, Davao City; the significant relationship between knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights of the students in District 1, Davao City; and the domains of knowledge regulation skills that predict the English literature insights of the students in District 1, Davao City.

3.1. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students—

3.1.1. *Planning*—In-service training in terms of planning is described as extensive, with a category mean of 3.54. This means that knowledge regulation skills of the students in terms of planning are oftentimes manifested among the students in District 1, Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.12 to 4.27. The item, Thinking about what I really need to learn before I begin a task reflects a mean rating of 3.12, described as moderately extensive, and interpreted as item is sometimes observed. Furthermore, the item Setting specific goals before I begin a task has a mean rating of 4.27, described as very extensive and inter-

preted as always manifested. This implies that the ability of students to effectively plan and organize their learning activities and strategies to achieve their educational goals is oftentimes observed. This finding is congruent to the view of Taufiqurachman (2021) students with high levels of knowledge regulation skills in planning can allocate their study time more efficiently. They can create structured study schedules that ensure they cover all necessary topics and assignments without last-minute cramming. Also, this agrees with the view of Alsaleh (2020) that students with strong planning skills can identify and access the most appropriate resources for their learning needs. They can select relevant textbooks, online materials, or research sources, ensuring their efforts are well-directed.

Table 1. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students in Terms of Planning

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Thinking about what I really need to learn before I begin a task.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2. Setting specific goals before I begin a task.	4.27	Very Extensive
3. Asking myself questions about the material before I begin.	3.68	Extensive
4. Thinking of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
5. Organizing my time to best accomplish my goals.	3.45	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.54	Extensive

3.1.2. *Information Management Strategies*—This dimension has a category mean of 3.10, described as moderately extensive, which means that this domain of knowledge regulation skills in District 1, Davao City is sometimes observed. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.44 to 3.48. Specifically, the item, Focusing on the meaning and significance of new information, shows a mean rating of 2.44, described as less extensive, interpreted as an item seldom manifested. The item, Focusing my attention consciously on important information, reflects a mean rating of 3.48, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. This implies that students’ ability to handle, organize, and

utilize information and resources in their learning processes is sometimes observed efficiently and effectively. This finding supports the assertion of Al’Omairi and Al Balushi (2015) that students with moderate knowledge regulation skills can effectively utilize learning resources in the English classroom, such as textbooks, online materials, and reference books. They can access information but may require guidance on optimizing its use. Likewise, the result supports Cicekc and Sadik’s (2019) idea that students with moderate skills in information management can conduct basic research for English assignments. They can find relevant sources and gather information but may require guidance to refine their research strategies and evaluate sources critically.

Table 2. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students in Terms of Information Management Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Slow down when I encounter important information.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
2. Focusing consciously on important information.	3.48	Extensive
3. Focusing on the meaning and significance of new information.	2.44	Less Extensive
4. Creating my own examples to make information more meaningful.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
5. Using the organizational structure of the text to help me learn.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.10	Moderately Extensive

3.1.3. *Comprehension Monitoring*—This particular domain of knowledge regulation skills in District 1, Davao City reflects an extensive category mean of 3.41 which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the junior high school students in District 1, Davao City. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.43 to 3.89. The table further re-

veals that the item Asking myself if I have considered all options when solving a problem has a mean rating of 2.43, described as less extensive, interpreted as an item seldom manifested. Meanwhile, the item Reviewing periodically to help me understand important relationships reflects a mean rating of 3.89, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. It

implies that students can effectively identify and address areas of confusion or misunderstanding in the context of their learning. This result supports the findings of Ozan and Kınca (2018) that high levels of comprehension monitoring skills enhance students’ ability to understand complex literary texts in English. They can recognize when they struggle to grasp a concept,

character, or theme and take proactive steps to address the issue, such as rereading or seeking clarification. They are more likely to engage in English class discussions actively. They can contribute thoughtfully, ask relevant questions, and seek clarification when encountering challenging or ambiguous content.

Table 3. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students in Terms of Comprehension Monitoring

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Asking myself periodically if I am meeting my goals.	3.56	Extensive
2. Considering several alternatives to a problem before I answer.	3.67	Extensive
3. Asking myself if I have considered all options when solving a problem.	2.43	Less Extensive
4. Reviewing periodically to help me understand important relationships.	3.89	Extensive
5. Finding myself analyzing the usefulness of strategies while I study.	3.52	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

3.1.4. *Debugging Strategies*—Likewise, regarding the dimension of debugging strategies, it reflects a category mean of 3.84, described as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes manifested among the students in District 1, Davao City. The mean ratings of the different items range from 3.51 to 4.13. Specifically, the item Stop-

ping and going back over new information that is not clear has a mean rating of 3.51, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. The item, Re-evaluating my assumptions when I get confused, reflects a mean of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested.

This implies that students can identify, address, and rectify errors, misconceptions, or gaps in their understanding of the English language and literature. This finding supports the assertion of Sil (2017) that high levels of debugging strategies skills are instrumental in improving writing skills in English. Students can identify and correct grammar, punctuation, and syntax errors, producing more polished and co-

herent essays, reports, and creative writing. This also supports Kabody’s (2013) idea that students with strong debugging skills excel in proofreading and editing their written work. They can identify spelling mistakes, typos, and structural issues, producing error-free documents.

3.1.5. *Evaluation*—Knowledge regulation skills in dimension on evaluation acquired a category mean of 3.27, described as moderately

Table 4. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students in Terms of Debugging Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Asking others for help when I don't understand something.	3.82	Extensive
2. Changing strategies when I fail to understand.	4.08	Extensive
3. Re-evaluating my assumptions when I get confused.	4.13	Extensive
4. Stopping and going back over new information that is not clear.	3.51	Extensive
5. Stopping and rereading when I get confused.	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.84	Extensive

extensive and sometimes manifested among the students in District 1, Davao City. The mean ratings of the different items range from 2.89 to 3.52. Specifically, the item Knowing how well I did once I finished a test has a mean rating of 2.89, described as moderately extensive, inter-

preted as an Overitem sometimes manifested. The item, Asking myself how well I accomplish my goals once I'm finished, reflects a mean of 3.52, described as extensive and interpreted as an item often manifested.

Table 5. Knowledge Regulation Skills of the Students in Terms of Evaluation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Knowing how well I did once I finished a test.	2.89	Moderately Extensive
2. Asking myself if there was an easier way to do things after I finish a task.	3.37	Moderately Extensive
3. Summarizing what I've learned after I finish.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
4. Asking myself how well I accomplish my goals once I'm finished.	3.52	Extensive
5. Asking myself if I learned as much as I could have once I finished a task.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderately Extensive

This implies that the students in District 1, Davao City, oftentimes analyze performance and strategy effectiveness after a learning episode. This finding supports Duman and Se-

merci's (2019) idea that evaluation is also an important aspect of language learning. Accordingly, an evaluation will help students know their strengths and weaknesses in the learning

process. By knowing those strengths and weaknesses, learners can improve their learning plan for a better learning process. In addition, this supports Dotson’s (2016) proposition that evaluation will develop learning goals. Table 6 shows the extent of knowledge regulation skills of students in District 1, Davao City. The overall mean of the knowledge regulation skills of students is 3.43, described as extensive, denoting that it is oftentimes manifested by students in District 1, Davao City. Also, it could be seen in the table that knowledge regulation skills in debugging strategies acquired the highest mean score of 3.84, which is described as extensive. In contrast, knowledge regulation skills in information management strategies acquired the lowest mean score of 3.10, described as moderately extensive. This suggests that students’ capacity to regulate, control, and optimize their

learning processes is oftentimes observed actively and intentionally. This finding aligns with Poth’s (2019) finding that students with high-level knowledge regulation skills can approach English texts with advanced comprehension strategies. They can set clear reading goals, monitor their understanding, and adjust their reading strategies to tackle complex literary works. This finding also supports Buku et al. (2016) assertion that high-level knowledge regulation skills foster advanced critical thinking abilities. Students can engage deeply with English literature, analyze complex themes, and assess the perspectives and arguments presented in texts. According to Sword (2021), students who know the different learning, thinking, and problem-solving strategies will be more likely to use them.

Table 6. Summary of Knowledge Regulation Skills of Students in District 1, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Planning	3.54	Extensive
Information Management Strategies	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Comprehension Monitoring	3.41	Extensive
Debugging Strategies	3.84	Extensive
Evaluation	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

3.2. English Literature Insights of Students—

3.2.1. Reaction of Social Injustice—The result in Table 7 shows that this particular domain of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, was assessed by the students as extensive with a category mean of 3.55, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.03 to 4.56. On the one hand, the item, Perceiv-

ing that English literature reflects what happens around us, like cruelty, hatred, and injustices, has a mean rating of 3.03, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item Literature tells us about bad things because most human beings hate violence, cruelty, and injustices, which reflects a mean of 4.56 described as very extensive, interpreted as always manifested.

Table 7. English Literature Insights of Students in Terms of Reaction to Social Injustice

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Liking some English writers such as Charles Dickens and George Orwell because they increased my level of understanding toward social injustices and refined my taste of English.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
2. Perceiving that English literature reflects what happens around us like cruelty, hatred, and injustices.	3.03	Moderately Extensive
3. Literature tells us about bad things because most human beings hate violence, cruelty, and injustices.	4.56	Very Extensive
4. Thinking of the movie “Animal Farm” when I see what happens in the Arab world as this novel talks about injustices and cruelty.	3.43	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.55	Extensive

The extensive rating on this domain implies that the idea reflecting the social justice prevailing in society is oftentimes manifested by the students in District 1, Davao City. The findings are congruent with the view of Coles (2019) that understanding literature paves the way for contemporary society and the eternal human mind and heart. Adding more, this finding agrees with the assertion of Irene (2015) that exploring literature can provide the historical, traditional, and cultural context of a particular era or age through fictional characters and delineating life and society then and their relevance to societal practices. This is one way to study social justice and its context. According to Sivapalan and Subramaniam (2014), literature is the only place where humans are treated as humans, not

with their caste, creed, and status.

3.2.2. *Understanding of Human Nature and Values*—In terms of understanding human nature and values, Table 8 shows a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.28, which means that this domain of English literature insights is oftentimes manifested by the students in District 1, Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.18 to 4.12. The item, Knowing about the feelings of jealousy and love, violence and selfishness because it raised my awareness about such values in all communities, and literature truly echoes the voice of community reflects a mean rating of 2.18, described as less extensive, interpreted as item seldom manifested.

Meanwhile, the item, Reading English Literature, helps me see the world around me with a better understanding, shows a rating of 4.12, is described as extensive, and is interpreted as an

item oftentimes manifested among the students. This suggests that the belief that literature expresses universal human nature is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This finding

Table 8. English Literature Insights of Students in Terms of Understanding of Human Nature and Values

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Knowing about the feelings of jealousy and love, violence, and selfishness because it raised my awareness about such values in all communities, and literature truly echoes the voice of community.	2.18	Less Extensive
2. Believing that English literature is like a beautiful sky above that covers the whole world.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
3. Believing that English literature makes us aware of what is good and bad around us.	3.98	Extensive
4. Reading English literature helps me see the world around me with a better understanding.	4.12	Extensive
5. Reading literature widened my gaze and let my thinking travel abroad.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

supports the view Shah et al. (2015) that literature is a reflection of humanity and a way for us to understand each other. Hence, by listening to the voice of another person readers can begin to figure out how that individual think. Additionally, the finding is in line with the assertion of Tevdovska (2016) that the ability to sense themes and messages opens us up to another way of thinking. Thus, it can increase knowledge and experience about human problems, including values, morals, cultures, and interests. After reading a literary work, the reader may get a certain impression of what they read as a product of human culture. Literature has its functions.

3.2.3. *Cultural Clashes*—Specifically, examining the domain of cultural clashes, results in Table 9 reveal that its category mean is 3.51, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain of English literature insights is oftentimes manifested. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges

from 2.43 to 4.24. It is noteworthy that item, Not liking English Literature because it clashes with mine, has a mean rating of 2.43, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item that is seldom manifested, while item, Not liking literature in general and especially English literature because it is different from our culture, habits, and religion has a mean rating of 4.24, described as very extensive and interpreted as item always manifested by the students in District 1, Davao City. The result implies that students’ ability to analyze, understand, and critically interpret literary works that explore conflicts and interactions between different cultures, traditions, or belief systems is oftentimes manifested by the students in District 1, Davao City. This finding supports the view of Dwaik et al. (2015) that high-level insights prepare students for effective intercultural communication. They are better equipped to engage in meaningful dialogues with individuals from different cultural backgrounds, both academically and personally.

Likewise, the findings agree with Skaar et al. (2018) assertion that English teaching benefits from students with high-level insights into cultural clashes as they develop advanced cultural competency. They can engage with literature from diverse cultural backgrounds, recognizing nuances and appreciating the complexities of intercultural interactions.

Table 9. English Literature Insights of Students in Terms of Cultural Clashes

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Not liking literature in general and especially English literature because it is different from our culture, habits, and religion.	4.24	Very Extensive
2. Not liking English literature because it clashes with mine.	2.43	Less Extensive
3. English literature is different from our culture and religion, but still writers can summarize general feelings about human beings.	3.89	Extensive
4. Feeling a lot of things similar about humanity though English culture and literature are different from my culture and religion.	3.47	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.51	Extensive

3.2.4. *Impact of Environment*—By examining the domain on the impact of environment, results in Table 10 reveal that its category mean is 3.51, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain on English literature insights is oftentimes manifested. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.51 to 4.08. It is noteworthy that item, Spending time reading English literature because my friends shared the same interest has a mean rating of 3.51, described as extensive and interpreted as item is oftentimes manifested, while item Loving English literature because one of my family members talked about it has a mean rating of 4.08, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the

students in District 1, Davao City. The result implies that students can recognize and appreciate the environmental context of literary texts and its significance. This finding supports the view of Teranishi et al. (2015) that high-level insights encourage the development of ecocritical thinking. Students can engage with literature that explores the relationships between humanity and the environment, fostering an understanding of ecological and environmental issues. English teaching benefits from students with high-level insights into the impact of the environment as they develop advanced environmental awareness. They can appreciate the role of nature, society, and culture in shaping the narratives of literary works.

Lastly, Table 11 summarizes the extent of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. As shown in the table, English literature insights of students obtained an over-

all mean score of 3.51, descriptively rated as extensive. Adding more, results on the table show that English literature insights in terms of the impact of the environment got the highest

Table 10. English Literature Insights of Students in Terms of Impact of Environment

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Loving English literature because one of my family members talked about it.	4.08	Extensive
2. Liking English literature because one of my family members talked about novels and plays.	3.69	Extensive
3. Spending time reading English literature because my friends shared the same interest.	3.51	Extensive
4. Reading English literature because it is a trend in our society nowadays.	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.74	Extensive

mean score of 3.68, descriptively rated as extensive. In contrast, English literature insights in terms of understanding human nature and values got the lowest mean score of 3.28, descriptively rated as moderately extensive. The findings imply that students' ability to analyze, interpret, and critically understand literary works is often-times observed in District 1, Davao City. This finding is congruent with McKay's (2015) view that high-level insights promote advanced critical thinking skills. Students can analyze complex themes, question assumptions, and explore the deeper layers of meaning in literature. Ac-

ording to Taharuddin (2018), English teaching benefits from students with high-level insights, as they engage in more advanced and nuanced literary analysis. They can critically evaluate literary elements, symbolism, and subtext within the text. Also, this finding supports Othman et al. (2015) argument that students with high-level insights are better prepared to contribute effectively to class discussions. They can articulate their interpretations, offer well-supported arguments, and engage in thoughtful debates about the text.

Table 11. Summary on English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Reaction to Social Injustices	3.55	Extensive
Understanding of Human Nature and Values	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Cultural Clashes	3.51	Extensive
Impact of Environment	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.51	Extensive

3.3. *Relationship Between Knowledge Regulation Skills and English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City* — The results of the analysis of the relationship be-

tween knowledge regulation skills and students' English literature insights are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine

the relationship between students' knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights in District 1, Davao City. Table 12 shows that knowledge regulation skills have a significant positive relationship with the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .885, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of knowledge regulation skills changes, the English literature insights of students in District 1 in Davao City also significantly change. Moreover, the table also shows that the knowledge regulation skills in terms of planning, information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation are significantly correlated with English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, as evidenced by the correlation coefficient values of 0.448, 0.618, 0.578, 0.602, and 0.661. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between knowledge reg-

ulation skills and students' English literature insights. The result implies that knowledge regulation skills improve English literature insights by promoting active reading, critical thinking, time management, and self-reflection. They empower students to engage deeply with literary texts, leading to more meaningful and insightful interpretations of the literature. The findings agree with Stefánsson's (2014) view that knowledge regulation skills encourage active reading. Students learn to set goals for their reading, which may include understanding the plot, character development, themes, and literary techniques. They continually monitor their comprehension and adjust their reading strategies if they encounter difficulties. This approach ensures that they engage more deeply with the text and grasp its subtleties. According to Whinne (2015), students with solid knowledge regulation skills can take notes while reading literature. They can identify critical points, noteworthy passages, and elements of interest.

Table 12. Relationship Between Knowledge Regulation Skills and English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Planning	0.448*	0.000	Reject H0
Information Management Strategies	0.618*	0.000	Reject H0
Comprehension Monitoring	0.578*	0.000	Reject H0
Debugging Strategies	0.602*	0.001	Reject H0
Evaluation	0.661*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Knowledge Regulation Skills	0.885*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

3.4. *Influence of Knowledge Regulation Skills on the English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City* —The significance of the influence of knowledge regulation

skills on the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, was analyzed using regression analysis. Table 13 shows that when knowledge regulation skills in terms of

planning, information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation are considered as predictors of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, the model is significant as evident in F-value of 32.294 with $p < 0.05$. Therefore, knowledge regulation skills predict the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.342 indicates that knowledge regulation skills have contributed significantly to the variability of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, by 38.60 percent from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 61.40 percent was credited to other factors not covered in this study. In addition, table shows that the domains of knowledge regulation skills significantly influence the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. This table also indicates that information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, and debugging strategies are significant when considering the predictors. This means that the extent of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City increases by 0.301, 0.256, and 0.225 for each unit of knowledge regulation skills. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the

domains of knowledge regulation skills significantly influence the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. Affirming that English literature insights are a function of knowledge regulation skills, the results agree with Zhang and Seepho's (2013) proposition that students with knowledge regulation skills engage in self-reflection and metacognition. They assess their understanding of the text and recognize when they encounter confusion or uncertainty. This self-awareness prompts them to seek clarification or additional information, resulting in improved insights. They are more likely to be intrinsically motivated to read and analyze texts when they have the tools to regulate their learning effectively. This motivation leads to a more thorough exploration of the material. Lastly, the finding supports Zimmerman and Schunk's (2001) Self-Regulated Learning Theory (SRL) that students' knowledge regulation skills can be framed within metacognition, where they set goals, monitor their understanding of literary texts, and evaluate their comprehension. The study can explore how students use these skills to adapt their strategies for reading, interpreting, and engaging with English literature, ultimately impacting their insights.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion follows statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the domains of knowledge regulation skills that significantly influence students' English literature insights. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling technique to select the respondents. The researcher selected 155 junior high school students in District 1, Davao City, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling

method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The knowledge regulation skills of students in District 1, Davao City, have an overall mean of 3.43 and a descriptive rating of extensive, while knowledge regulation skills in terms of planning, information man-

Table 13. Influence of Knowledge Regulation Skills on the English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City

Knowledge Regulation Skills	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Planning	-0.224	-0.108	0.039	0.156	Accept H0
Information Management Strategies	0.301*	0.423	0.046	0.001	Reject H0
Comprehension Monitoring	0.256*	0.327	0.048	0.000	Reject H0
Debugging Strategies	0.225*	0.284	0.039	0.000	Reject H0
Evaluation	-0.197	-0.293	0.051	0.104	Accept H0
R²	0.386				
F-value	32.294*				
p-value	0.000				

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

agement strategies, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation obtained mean scores of 3.54, 3.10, 3.41, 3.84, and 3.27, respectively. English Literature Insights of Students in District 1, Davao City, has an overall mean of 3.51 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, English Literature Insights in terms of reaction to social injustice, understanding of human nature and values, cultural clashes, and impact of environment obtained mean scores of 3.55, 3.28, 3.51, and 3.68, respectively. Pearson Moment Product Correlation analysis showed that knowledge regulation skills have a significant positive relationship with the English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .885$, $p < 0.05$). Regression analysis underscored the predictive power of knowledge regulation skills in the context of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. When factors such as planning, information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation were considered, the model was significant, as indicated by an

F-value of 32.294 with $p < 0.05$. The computed adjusted R2 value of 0.342 further confirmed that knowledge regulation skills contribute significantly to the variability of English literature insights, accounting for 38.60 percent of the total variability. Information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, and debugging strategies emerged as significant predictors of English literature insights.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The knowledge regulation skills of students in District 1, Davao City, were found to be extensive, a positive reflection of their cognitive abilities. Specifically, information management strategies and evaluation were rated moderately extensive, while planning, comprehension monitoring, and debugging strategies were rated as extensive. This suggests that the students’ ability to manage their thinking processes allows them to think strategically, solve problems, set goals, organize ideas, and evaluate what is known and not known. English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, were described as extensive. English Lit-

erature Insights regarding understanding human nature and values were rated moderately extensive. In contrast, English Literature Insights regarding social injustice, cultural clashes, and the impact of the environment were rated as extensive. This indicates that students often manifest insight and understanding of individuals concerning literature. Further, knowledge regulation skills were significantly correlated with English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. This indicates that as the extent of knowledge regulation skills changes, English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City, also significantly change. Furthermore, it was found that the model was significant when knowledge regulation skills in planning, information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, debugging strategies, and evaluation are considered predictors of English literature insights of students in District 1, Davao City. Knowledge regulation skills in information management strategies, comprehension monitoring, and debugging strategies are significant predictors of English literature insights.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The Department of Education (DepEd) may encourage the integration of metacognitive strategies and knowledge regulation skills in educational policy and curriculum development. It may also promote the inclusion of explicit metacognition instruction and consider including metacognitive assessments as part of

standardized testing to ensure students develop knowledge regulation skills alongside subject-specific knowledge. School principals may ensure that teachers have access to resources and materials that support the development of knowledge regulation skills and English literature insights. They should invest in library resources, technology, and professional development opportunities. They should also create a school culture that values metacognition and knowledge regulation. They may emphasize the importance of reflection, self-assessment, and self-regulated learning among students and teachers. English teachers may incorporate explicit metacognition and knowledge regulation instruction into the English curriculum. They may teach students to set learning goals, monitor their comprehension, and adapt their strategies. They may also provide individualized feedback on students' reading and analysis, encourage students to reflect on their comprehension and analysis, and offer guidance for improvement. Students may reflect on their reading and analysis process. Consider what strategies were effective and which areas require improvement. Continuously work on strengthening your knowledge regulation skills. Students may continually monitor their comprehension while reading. If they encounter confusion or uncertainty, they can take notes, ask questions, or seek clarification to enhance their understanding. Lastly, researchers may conduct further analysis on the factors that influence the students' English literature insights since knowledge regulation skills contributed 38.60

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